
Bhartrhari's Criticism in Jain Logic: A Study

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The grammarian-philosopher Bhartrhari opines that *Sabda* is the substratum of the world of appearance and thus he accepts the theory of *Sabdadvaita*. However, this key-stone of the Grammarians' system of metaphysics has elaborately been controverted by the rival schools. Here we propose to record the dialectics of the Jaina philosophers, one of the rival schools of metaphysics.

This theory of Bhartrhari has been subjected to severe criticism by the *Naiyayikas*, *Mimamsakas*, Buddhists and Jainas. Now, for our practical purpose we discuss the view of the Jaina logicians like Vidyanandi (9th century A.D.), Abhayadev Suri (11th century A.D.), Prabhacandra (1st half 12th Century A.D.), Vadideva Suri (second half of 12th Century, A.D.) and Yasovijaya Gani (18th Century A.D.).

The Jaina logicians argue that the *Sabdabrahman* is a *prameya* and a *prameya* needs a *pramana* for its recognition (1). There is no *pramana* through which we can prove the existence of the *Sabdabrahman* (2).

In the *Tattavarthaslokavartika*, Vidyanandi opines that the *Sabdabrahman* is not proved by perception, inference and verbal Testimony (3). This standpoint of Vidyanandi is also supposed by Santaraksita, Abhayadeva, Prabhacandra and Vadideva. However, Prabhacandra and Vadideva ask the grammarians during their discussion that the *Sabdabrahman* is recognised by *indriyajanya pratyaksa* or by *atindriya pratyaksa* or by *Svasamvedanasila pratyaksa*? The first alternative is not qualified enough to recognise the *Sabdabrahman* as it is not recognised by the Jaina Logicians. They argue that this type of *pratyaksa* is illusory like the perception during dream (4). Thus, the sensual perception may not be taken as a cause of the perception of the *Sabdabrahman*. In the *Sanmatitarka Prakarana* it has been argued that a sense perceives that which is present and which is also large (*sthula*) in nature. Therefore,

the *Sabdabrahman* is not perceived by the sense organs. This is also supported by Prabhacandra in his *Prameyakamalamartanda* (5). During the discussion, both Prabhacandra and Vadideva Suri raise the same question — by which sense organ do we receive the *Sabdabrahman*? either by *Srotrendriya* or by any other *indriya* (6). Since the *Sabdabrahman* is beyond the subject of the *Srotrendriya* that may not be a cause to know the *Sabdabrahman*. If we accept that this is subject of the *Srotrendriya*, then we have to accept that everything should be known by each and every *indriya* (sense organ). But it is not possible to accept. Again, in the *Nyayakumudacandra* it has been explained that the other sense organs (i.e. other than *Srotrendriya*) also are not qualified enough because for the perception of the *Sabdabrahman*; because *Sabda* may not be a subject of any other sense organ other than the *Srotrendriya* (7). Thus, it may be concluded that the *Sabdabrahman* is not recognised by the *indriyajanya pratyaksa*.

The *Sabdabrahman* is also not a subject of the *atindriyapratyaksa*. In the *Nyaya-Kumuda Candra*, Prabhacandra opines that the *anindriyapratyaksa* without any sense organ is not accepted by the grammarians and therefore, that should not be the cause to establish the *Sabdabrahman* (8). In the reply the grammarians argue that a Yogi realises the existence of the SB (*Sabdabrahman*) through *Dhyana* and therefore the existence of the SB is proved by *atindriyapratyaksa* of the Yogis. Now the Jaina logicians again argue that if the SB is the only ultimate reality, then who will be there to realise it? and if we accept to the Yogis, then we have to accept the Yoga also. Thus, the concept of *advaita* 'non-duality' will no more exist (9).

Further, Prabhacandra and Vadideva Suri ask the opponents that if there exists the SB then why do we not feel the existence of that? Here they give two alternatives:

- (i) Due to the absence of *Grahaka* (*Grahakatvabhava*)
- (ii) Due to the *Avidya* (*Avidyabhibhuta*) (10).

We may not say that due to the first alternative the SB is not manifested, because, in the *Sabdadvaitasiddhanta* the SB is *grahaka* and the *grahaka-Sakti* always exists in it: (11) and the second alternative also is not possible as the existence of *Avidya* is not recognized by the Jaina logicians. It is not out of context to mention that in the *Nyayakumudacandra*. Prabhacandra categorical rejects the existence of the *Dvaividya* (12). This standpoint of Prabhacandra is also supported by *Vadideva* suri in the

Syadvadaratnakara (13). In this context the Jaina logicians again argue that since the *grahaka-sakti* exists always in the SB, we cannot say that due to the absence of the *grahaka-Sakti* the SB does not manifest. Again, Prabhacandra and Vadideva Suri argue that *Avidya* is neither identical with SB not with other than the SB (14) and if it is other than the SB then either it is a *vastu* or it is *avastu*? Both these alternatives have been rejected by the Jaina logicians in their respective works and therefore, according to them, *avidya* is neither a *vastu* nor an *avastu* viz. (*na ca laghepa praheyatgayasya brahmanah tadasat tathapratibhaso muktotiprasangat napyavasturad vastuno nyathabhavo bhavati atiprasangat ca* (N.K.C. p.143) and *atha vastuth tanna, abhyupagamaksatiprasakteh* (ibid. 1/5, p.143). Thus, the existence of the *avida* has been rejected by the Jainas and it may be suggested that like the *Indriya-pratyaksa*, the SB is also not proved by *the Anindriya-pratyasa*.

Now we should think about the *Svasamvedanapratyaksa*. According to Vidyanandi if the knowledge which is *ksanika* and *niramsa* (Buddhists views) is not proved by the above *pratyasa*, then how shall we establish the existence of the SB by the said *Pratyaksa* (15)? In this connection, Prabhacandra says that during dream (*Svapnavastha*) we cannot feel the SB which manifests with *atmajyoti*, by the *svasamvedanapratyaksa* otherwise, each and every creature will attend liberation without any effort. Because it has been categorically mentioned in the *Advaita-sabda-siddhanta* that the *svasamvedanatva* of SB, which manifests with *atmajyoti* is liberation. Again, he explains that if the SB will be *svasamvedanasila*, then the words like *ghata* and *pata* should be *svasamvedanasila*, as these words are the *vivarta* of the SB. But this is not accepted, because all the words are not *svasamvedanasila*. Thus, the Jaina logicians argue that the SB is not perceived by *svasamvedana-pratyaksa* (16). Now we may conclude that the existence of the SB is not proved by perception.

Like perception, the existence of SB is also not proved by inference, another means of the valid knowledge. Secondly, it is also a fact that the inference is not recognized by *Sabdavaitavadis* as a way of valid knowledge. In this connection, Vadideva Says that: *napyaymanena, tasya tatsadbhavavedakasya kasyacidasambhavati* (17). *Acarya* Vidyanandi also explains vividly regarding this problem. According to him since in the *Sabdadvaitaisiddhanta*, inference is not recognized as a means of valid-knowledge, how

can we prove the existence of the SB by inferences (18):

Again, the Jain logicians ask that by which inference the *Sabdadvaitavadins* prove the existence of SB; either by *Karyalinganumana* or by *Svabhavalinganumana* (19)? This is also supported by Abhayadeva Suri and Prabhacandra (20). According to Jaina scholars the first alternative is not justified here, because the eternal SB has an action; neither it has any action chronologically (*arthakriya*), nor it has any action collectively. If there is no action, then how can we, say that the SB may be established through *Karyalinganumana*. The second alternative also has no scope to prove the existence of the SB; because it is needed first to establish the existence of the *dharmi* SB and after that only we can prove it by inference, which is the *Svarupabhutadharma* of the SB. But when the *Dharmi* SB, has no existence, then its *Svabhavalinga* is automatically regarded as non-existence. Thus, the SB is not established by inference, the second way of valid knowledge.

In the *Tattvartha-Sloka-varttika*, Vidyanandi refutes the possibility that the SB is proved by the means of Verbal Testimony. He says :

agamadeva tat-siddhau bhedasiddhistatha na kim.

nirbadhat-eva cettacyam na pramanamatarad-rte,(21)

Further, he explains that the followers of the *Sabdadvaita* concepts say the existence of the SB is recognized by verbal testimony, which is free from any kind of obstacles (*badharahita*). Here Vidyanandi does not support the *nirbadhatva* of the verbal testimony as there is no valid knowledge to prove this (22).

Again, an interesting doubt has been raised by Jaina logicians like Vidyanandi, Prabhacandra and Vadideva Suri that the SB is identified with verbal testimony or the SB is separate from the verbal testimony? In the Case of former alternative, the verbal testimony may not be a cause for the establishment of the SB due to the lack of the relation of cause and effect (*karya-karana bhava*). The second alternative is also impossible here, because if we accept two things like the SB and the verbal testimony, then the *advaita* "non-duality" character of the SB will no longer exist. It is needless to say here again that the grammarians accept the SB as "non-duality", and says everything is produced from it viz.:

tad-agamasya niscetum sakyam jatu pariksakaith.

nacagamastato nginnah samasti paramarthatah (23).

To refute the objection of the Jaina logicians, the grammarians may argue that verbal testimony is the *vivarta* of the SB. However, Vidyanandi nicely rejects this type of argument of the grammarians. According to him if the verbal testimony or will be the *vivarta* "appearance" of the SB like other things, then this means of knowledge will be treated as *avidya*, which is *asat*. Now he asks the opponents that an *asat*, i.e. the verbal testimony may not be a cause for a *sat* one i.e. the SB viz *tad-vivartastva vidyatma tasya prajnapakah katham* (24). Thus, the verbal testimony may not be a case to prove the existence of the SB.

In the *Tattvarthaslokavarttika*, Vidyanandi not only rejects the existence of the SB, but directly attains Bhartrhari quoting his first verse from the *Vakyapadiya*. He also opines that there is no such type of *Brahman* who is without beginning or end, whose very essence is the word, who is the cause of the manifested phenomenon, who appears as the objects from whom the creation of the world proceeds viz.

tato natva oaram brahmastyanadinidhanatmakam.

Vivarte-tvarthabhavena prakriya jagato yatah (25).

Thus, the Jaina logician rejects the existence of the SB, which is, according to the grammarians, the real cause of this universe. They not only reject the existence of the SB, but also argue that the world is not engulfed with words "*Sabdamaya*". According to them since the SB is eternal in character, how any change "*vivarta* or *parinama*" is possible with that? Again, they think if the grammarians argue that at the time of change the SB leaves its own quality or not? As the SB is eternal, the first alternative does not seem to be possible and if the second will be accepted, then, as all the things are engulfed with SB, a dwarf "*Vadhira*" will be able to listen everything after seeing the things produced from the SB viz. *rupa samvedana samaya vadhira sya sabdasamvedana prasanga* etc (26).

Like this, the Jainas, studied the philosophy of grammar in general and Bhartrhari especially and rejected the view that the world is produced from the SB, which is eternal and the world is engulfed with words. Besides, they reject the theories like: knowledge in general is *Sabdanuiddha*, there is eternal relation

between *sabda* and *artha* etc. These kinds of studies among the Jainas had taken place in between 9th century A.D. to 19th century A.D. The Jainas not only studied the philosophical side of the Sanskrit grammar, but they also prepared their own treatises on the word-formation, some of the works are critically edited and published, but many works are still in manuscript forms.

References:

1. The Mimansakas also argue that *prameya* is recognised only by *pramana*, viz., *manadhina-meya-siddhi*. Abhaydeva Suri in *sanmatitaraka-prakaranatika* says ; *pramanadhina hi prameyavyavastha* (p.334)
2. Cf. *na ca evambhuta brahmasiddhaye pramanam-upa; abhayate* , !bid, 3rd Pt., Gatha 6; p. 384.
3. Cf. *brahmano na vyavasthanam-aksajnanit kutacara*.
4. Cf. *brahmano na vyavasthanam-aksajnanit kutacara. svapnadaviva mithyatvattasya sakalpatah svayani*The *Tattvarthaslakavarttika* 1/3, sutra 20, Kanike-97, p.240. Also *Tattvartha sutra* (with explanation) Bombay, I am 1940, p.21.
5. Cf. *na khaly yathopavarnitasvarupam sabdabrahma pratyaksath praciyaate, sanvada pratiniyatartha svarupagradaktvenaivasua pratieh*. The *Prameyakamala-marittanda*, 1/3, Bombay, 1941, p. 45.
6. Ref. the *Nyayakumudacandra*, 1/3, p.142.
7. Refer the *Syadvadaratnakara*. VII/6. p.78 and the *Nyayakumudacandra*, 1/5, p.142.
8. Cf; *napyatindriyapratyaksad; tasyaivatuasambhavat*; Prabhacandra on the *Nyayakumudacandra*, p. 142; also the *Syadvadaratnakara*, 1/ 7, p, 99.
9. Ibid.
10. *Athasti kasmanna prakasate-grahakabhavat avidyabhibhutavada*. The *Nyayakumudacandra*, 1/5, p. 142.
11. Cf. *grahyatvam grahakatvam ca dve sakti tejaso yatha tathaiva sarvasabdanamete prthagavasthite*. The *Vakyapadiya*, 1-55.

12. CI; *sahibrahmano vyatirikta atiaikia va?* etc. The *Nyayakumudacandra* 1/5, p. 143.
13. Cf; *sahi sabdobrahmanah sakasabhinna bhaved-abhinna va*, 11/7, p. 99.
14. Refer note 12 above.
15. Cf; *svatahssamvedaiatsiddhihksanikandmsavittivat. na parabrahmano napi sa yukta sadhanadvina*. The *Tattvarthaslokavarttika* 1/3, sutra 20, p. 240.
16. CI; *na ca ghatadisabarho va svasamviditas vabhavah yatastadanvitatvam svasam vedamatah siddhayet, asvasamviditasvabhavatayaivasyapratipraniprasiddhatvat*. The *Nyayakumuda-candra*, 115, p. 144.
17. The *Syadvadtratnakara* 1/7, p. 100.
18. Cf. *nanundariattatorthanampratitidurVabhatvatah. paraprasiddhirapyasya prasiddhanapramanika*, The *Tattvarthaslokavarttika*, 1/3, Sutra, 20 Verse-97, p. 240.
19. Cf. *napyannmmanatah / tatha hi anumanam bhavat-karyalingam bhavet svabhavalingam va?* Kamalasila on *Tattvarthasamgraha-panjika-tika* verses 147-148, pp. 92-93.
20. Refer the *Sanmatitarkaprakaranatika*, Gatha-6 p. 384 and the *Prameyakamalamartanda*, 1/3, p. 45
21. The *Tattvarthasiokavarttika* 1/3, Sutra - 20, Verse-99, p.241,
22. In the commentary the author opines that: *na hi bharantiriyamakhilabhedapratitir-ityaniscaye tadanyathanupapattya tadbijabhuttam sabdatattvam anadinidhanam brahma sidhyati/* etc. Ibid, p. 241.
23. Ibid, verse 100; also the *Prameyakamalamartanda*. IV/3, p.46, also the *Syadvadtratnakara* 1/7, pp. 101.
24. The *Tattvarthaslokavarttika*, Ibid verse 101, p. 241,
25. Ibid, verse 103, p. 241.
26. The *Sammatitarkappanatika*, p. 381